

SUPPLEMENT: The Gut Microbiome and Allergic Asthma in the Swedish Twin Study on Prediction and Prevention of Asthma (STOPPA) Cohort

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Abstract

Background: Asthma is a common chronic and complex childhood disease. Changes in the gut microbiome have been associated with asthma, but little is known about the gut microbiome in pre-adolescents with allergic asthma, or the impact of shared familial factors. The aim of this study was to investigate the association between bacterial signatures in the gut microbiome and allergic asthma.

Methods: Detailed clinical information, blood and fecal samples from twin children recruited in the Swedish *T*win Study *on* Prediction and Prevention of Asthma (STOPPA) cohort were collected at 9-14 years. Shotgun metagenomic sequencing was used to analyze fecal samples, and blood samples were used to determine specific Immunoglobulin (Ig)-E levels in a cross-sectional study. Children were classified as allergic asthma, asthma only, IgE sensitization only and healthy controls.

Findings: A total of 317 children (129 twin pairs and 59 singletons) were included in the full microbiome analysis, with exposure groups similar in age, birthweight, zygosity and mode of delivery. While there was little or no evidence for difference in overall species richness or -composition between exposure groups, a total of $n=201$ species was found to be differentially abundant between healthy controls and at least one exposed group ($FDR \leq 0.01$) after adjustment for twin pairs. The strongest signal was found for microbial families *Streptococaceae* ($n = 63$) and *Lachnospiracaceae* ($n = 40$). However, when the differential abundance in the asthma only and IgE sensitized exposures were examined, the microbiome data had negligible ability to predict allergic asthma, when assuming a non-additive model.

Conclusion: In this adolescent twin population, we found no difference in overall microbial composition between children with allergic asthma and healthy controls. However, we observed considerable variation between twin pairs. Further, additive contributions of differentially abundant taxa for asthma and IgE sensitization may indicate that our results are due to medication use or possibly non-bacterial microbial colonization.

Abbreviations

ANCOMBC - Analysis of Compositions of Microbiomes with Bias Correction

DA - Differentially Abundant

IgE – Immunoglobulin E

OTU – Operational Taxonomic Units

PERMANOVA - Permutation-based Multivariate Analysis of Variance

STOPPA - Swedish Twin Study on Prediction and Prevention of Asthma

Key words: allergic asthma; children; gut microbiome; shotgun metagenomics sequencing; STOPPA; twin study

Key Message

- Using shotgun metagenomics, we found pairs differed strongly in global gut microbiome composition, but exposure groups did not.
- Per-feature analysis identified n=201 taxa differentially abundant (DA) in asthma-/IgE-sensitized exposure groups.
- 63/201 DA taxa fell into family Streptococcaceae and were consistently overabundant in asthma-/IgE-sensitized exposure groups.

Background

Asthma is a common chronic inflammatory disease characterized by wheezing, shortness of breath, chest tightness and cough, and frequently part of a triad involving eczema, allergic rhinitis and/or sensitization to Immunoglobulin (Ig)-E antibodies [1]. While the airway microbiome has naturally formed the focus of asthma studies, a growing body of literature supports the hypothesis that the onset of allergic disease, and by extension asthma development, lies partly in the microbial communities in the gastrointestinal tract [2]. Early life exposures associated with asthma in childhood include the use of antibiotics [3], mode of delivery [4] and the presence of siblings [5]. They may act by modifying the microbiome, which in turn may cause immune dysregulation and predispose to allergic disease [6]. However, the impact of these factors on the gut microbiome has not been consistent across studies.

Microbes are highly adapted to survive within complex community structures and facilitate diverse processes such as digestion, secretion of antimicrobial substances and utilizing nutrients from other microbes and/or host processes [7]. Commensal microbes are important in the development of the intestinal epithelia, instrumental in the normal development and function of the immune system, and play a key role in host metabolic and physiological processes [8]. Although studies fully describing the healthy composition of the gut microbiome in adolescent children are still lacking, it is critical to metabolic and immune system programming from birth [9]. It has been shown that the microbiome in early life is relatively volatile, and whilst microbial diversity increases and volatility stabilizes by around age 3, [10], there are few studies that show whether changes occur during the pubescent stage.

Emerging evidence suggests that asthma and taxa-specific shifts in abundance of specific bacteria in the gut microbiome are interrelated [11]. In a Canadian study (n=319), the reduction in the bacterial genera *Lachnospira*, *Veillonella*, *Faecalibacterium* and *Rothia* during the first 100 days of life was associated with the development of asthma and allergic diseases [12]. These findings were replicated in a Turkish study where both *Faecalibacterium*s and *Akkermansia* were similarly implicated [13]. *Clostridium sp* have also been demonstrably higher in asthma and atopic disease in some studies [14]. Most of these studies were conducted in very young children with no follow up studies examining gut microbial diversity in early adolescence. Additionally, most studies do not distinguish different asthma phenotypes and endotypes.

While individuals differ in their specific bacterial lineages, the composition of the gut microbiome is partly shared among family members, and displays a comparable degree of covariation between monozygotic and dizygotic twins [15]. This observation is however not consistent with findings by Stewart et al who reported that the bacterial community was more similar between identical twins than between non-identical twins [16]. In a Taiwanese twin study (n=30), an increase of *Ruminococcus gnavus* was observed before the onset of allergic manifestations in discordant twins [17].

Whilst genotype and environmental exposure influence the gut microbiome [9], novel metagenomic studies on childhood asthma are lacking. Most studies are conducted in children aged <7 years, primarily focus on early life microbial diversity, do not distinguish between different asthma phenotypes or take shared familial factors into account. Thus,

our aim was to study the association between gut microbial patterns and factors associated with increased allergic asthma in a well characterized Swedish cohort of twin children aged 9 to 14.

Supplementary Methods

Study Population and Design

This is a population-based study of Swedish twin children. Participants were recruited from the *Swedish Twin Study on Prediction and Prevention of Asthma (STOPPA) Cohort* [18]. STOPPA is a cohort nested in the *Child and Adolescent Twin Study in Sweden* cohort and based on asthma status [18, 19]. Per protocol, twins completed written standardized questionnaires and participated in clinical examinations [18]. In a clinical setting, blood and faecal samples were collected, and lung function testing conducted. Information on perinatal factors, diagnoses and medication were collected from national health registers [18].

Children were eligible if informed consent was provided by both them and their parents/legal guardians, if a questionnaire was answered and fecal samples provided. From the 376 twin pairs (752 individual twins) aged 9-14 included in STOPPA, 355 individual children provided fecal samples, **Supp. Figure 1**. Further information about the study cohort has been published previously [18].

Exposure status

Allergic asthma was defined as a composite outcome based on an asthma diagnosis and raised serum IgE. The parental response to the question current asthma (yes/no) was used to define asthma [20]. Blood samples from participants were analyzed for IgE-reactivity against inhalant allergens (including house dust, house dust mites, animal allergens including cat, horse and dog, pollen and birch, mugwort and fungal spores). Allergen reactivity was measured using Phadiatop® (ThermoFisher Scientific, Uppsala, Sweden), and defined as positive if ≥ 0.35 kU_A/l [21]. Those with a raised IgE level but no asthma were classified as IgE+ sensitized, while children with neither asthma nor raised IgE levels (IgE-) were included as healthy controls.

Variables collected.

From the STOPPA questionnaire, we extracted age (continuous); sex (male/female); zygosity (monozygotic/dizygotic/twin not in study) and mode of delivery (vaginal/cesarean section).

Sample Collection and Processing

A single stool sample was collected from each child between May 2011 and June 2014. Participants collected samples in a container and froze samples at home at -18°C in a pre-frozen transport container. They were then stored at -80°C at the Karolinska Institutet Biobank.

Sequencing and Annotation

Samples were extracted and sequenced at the Center for Translational Microbiome Research (CTMR) as previously described [22]. Briefly, samples were extracted using a modified version of the Zymo Quick-DNA Magbead Plus kit with physical and chemical lysis (Zymo Research, Irvine, CA, USA). Sequencing was performed using a 2x150 paired end strategy on DNBSeg-G400 (MGI, China).

Bioinformatic processing was performed using the StaG (v 0.4.1) Snakemake workflow [23, 24]. Quality filtering and control were performed using fastp [25]. Human reads were removed by mapping them against the 38th release of the human genome reference consortium using kraken2 [22, 26, 27]. Taxonomic tables were constructed using kraken2 with the Genome Taxonomy Database (release 89) [26, 28]. The table was then filtered to remove features not mapped to the phylogenetic tree.

Statistics

Categorical and continuous demographic variables and birth characteristics were reported as percentages and means (standard deviation), respectively. Microbial data generated by the bioinformatics pipeline, consisting of annotated species with their inferred phylogenetic tree and the corresponding table of OTU counts per sample, were imported into the R statistical software [29] using the Bioconductor package phyloseq (v. 1.34.0) [30]. Microbial data was quality-filtered by removing samples with failed assays or abnormally low sequencing depth (defined as $<1 \times 10^6$ total mapped reads per sample), as well as species with very low abundance (defined as <50 total reads across samples) or prevalence (defined as present in less than 5% of samples), **Supp. Figure 1**.

In a further pre-processing step, sequencing counts were rarefied to 1×10^6 reads prior to calculating and comparing microbial diversity between exposure levels. Alpha-diversity (within-sample biodiversity) was quantified using Shannon- and Simpson-indices; differences between exposure levels were assessed using mixed linear models accounting for correlations within twin pairs and adjusted for sequencing run. Beta-diversity (community similarity across samples) was quantified via appropriate dissimilarity measures between samples (weighted and unweighted UniFrac distances, [31, 32] and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity); differences between exposure levels were assessed via permutation-based multivariate analysis of variance [33] (PERMANOVA) using $k=999$ permutations and adjusting for sequencing run, examination location (five locations in Sweden) and twin pair number as potential confounders.

Per-species differential abundance analysis between exposure levels was performed using analysis of compositions of microbiomes with bias correction [34] (ANCOMBC) applied to the un-rarefied microbial data. ANCOMBC-specific

parameters were set to filtering OTUs with more than 50% missing values and use of classic (non-robust) standard errors, based on sensitivity analyses assessing between-analysis consistency (not shown). As primary analysis, we considered a three-group one-way design comparing each exposed group to healthy controls, as described above; we also fit an equivalent two-way factorial model with interaction between asthma and IgE+ to test for non-additive effects in allergic asthma as secondary analysis. All ANCOMBC models were adjusted for twin-pairs.

Supplementary Results

Quality filtering of samples and taxa yielded a total of more than 8.6×10^9 reads, representing 339 participants and 4,461 distinct taxa (**data set (A)** in **Supp. Figure 1**). Of these 339 children, 43 (13.6%) suffered from allergic asthma, 18 (5.7%) from asthma only, and 91 (28.7%) had raised IgE levels but no asthma (IgE+ allergic); in comparison, 165 (52%) had neither asthma nor elevated IgE levels (healthy controls). As expected, we found more boys than girls with raised IgE (69.2% vs 30.8%) and allergic asthma (65.1% vs 34.9%), respectively. In contrast, we found little variation in zygosity or mode of delivery between exposure levels. Overall, 258 (81%) of the children had a matching twin in the cohort, **Supp. Table 1**.

The median number of reads per sample was 22.3×10^6 across all 339 samples, with little variation across the exposure groups and samples with missing exposure information, **Supp. Figure 2**. For the full sample, the 11 most common microbial families cover 91% of all reads, with the four most common families (*Bacteroidaceae*, *Lachnospiraceae*, *Ruminococcaceae* and *Ruminococcaceae*) alone covering 65%, with little variation between groups, **Supp. Figure 3**.

Diversity analysis

For assessing the diversity of the microbial population, the raw quality-filtered **data set (A)**, **Supp. Figure 1** was rarefied to 1×10^6 reads for each of the 339 samples. Alpha- and beta diversity measures were calculated from this rarefied **data set (B)** in **Supp. Figure 1**, and only the $n=317$ samples with non-missing exposure information were used for comparing diversity between exposure groups.

We found no statistically significant evidence for differences in within sample alpha diversity between exposure groups, either before (Shannon: $p=0.39$, Simpson: $p=0.29$) or after adjustment for shared twin effects (Shannon: $p=0.59$, Simpson: $p=0.33$), **Supp. Figure 4**. The alpha diversity values however show reduced variability after adjustment, suggesting variability in alpha diversity between twin pairs.

We found no statistically significant evidence for differences in overall species composition between exposure groups in unadjusted analyses, for either the phylogenetically informed measures (weighted and unweighted UniFrac distance) or the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity: the asthma/allergy phenotypes explained approximately 1% of the variability in microbial community composition for all three beta-diversity measures, **Supp. Table 2**. After adjustment for sequencing run, geographical sampling site and shared twin effects, the amount of variability was reduced to 0.5-0.8%, with marginal significance for the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity but with no statistical significance for the UniFrac distances, providing little or no evidence for systematic difference in species composition between asthma phenotypes.

The largest explanatory factor for microbial composition, regardless of diversity measure, was twin pair ($R^2=66-71\%$, all $p=0.001$). In contrast, geographical sampling site explained 1.4-1.6%, and sequencing run 1.8-3.3% of variability.

Differentially abundant taxa across exposure groups

Running ANCOMBC on the quality-filtered data with an extra 50% prevalence filter (**data set (C)**, **Supp. Figure 1**) provided inference for 1,969 species, corresponding to 93% of all quality-filtered reads. 201 of the 1,969 assessed taxa (10%) were statistically significantly differentially abundant (DA) between the healthy control group and at least one of the three exposure levels at an FDR level $\leq 1\%$. Complete ANCOMBC results for all three exposure groups are listed in **Supp. Table 3**.

The majority of DA species were specific to a single exposure group (n=175; 87%), i.e. asthma only (n=68; 34%), IgE+ allergic (n=34; 17%) and allergic asthma groups (n=73; 36%), **Supp. Figure 5a**. Little overlap was found between the asthma only and IgE+ allergic groups (n=4; 2%), while allergic asthma shared slightly more DA taxa with both the asthma only and IgE+ allergic groups (n=9; 4.5% and n=13; 6.5%, respectively). Most of the overlap between allergic asthma and the other two exposure groups was concentrated in family Streptococcaceae, **Supp Figure 5c**.

We found that the eight most common microbial families among all DA taxa covered 77% of DA taxa, compared to 70% for taxa DA for asthma alone, and 82% for IgE+ allergy and allergic asthma DA taxa, **Supp. Figure 5b**. Similarly, the four most common families (*Streptococcaceae*, *Lachnospiraceae*, *Ruminococcoceae* and *Bacteroidaceae*) alone already accounted for 68% (pooled across exposures), 56% (asthma alone), 75% and 77% (IgE+ allergic and allergic asthma, respectively) of all taxa DA in their category. However, the actual distribution of families within each exposure level differed widely, with the proportions of DA *Streptococcaceae* and *Lachnospiraceae* taxa more similar between the IgE+ allergic- and allergic asthma groups, and the proportion of DA *Ruminococcoceae* and *Bacteroidaceae* more similar between the asthma alone- and IgE+ allergic groups. The overall most common family of DA taxa, *Streptococcaceae*, was very low-abundant in the raw quality-filtered data, accounting for only 0.13% of reads across samples, whereas the other three common families of DA taxa represent the three most common taxa in the raw quality-filtered data (**Supp. Figure 3**).

We mapped microbial families and statistical significances of the 201 DA taxa to their phylogenetic tree, **Supp. Figure 5c**. DA *Streptococcaceae* taxa were phylogenetically closely related, with most taxa statistically significantly DA for allergic asthma, followed by the IgE+ allergic group and the asthma-only group. In contrast, DA *Lachnospiraceae* taxa showed more phylogenetic diversity, and were mostly DA for asthma-only, followed by allergic asthma and the IgE+-allergic group. *Ruminococcoceae* taxa were mostly DA for asthma-only and the IgE+ allergic group, with some phylogenetic separation between the two groups of taxa. Species from *Bacteroidaceae* were mostly DA for allergic asthma, followed by asthma-only and IgE+ allergic. The *Other* category of DA taxa represents a diverse collection of rare and only loosely related taxa spread around the phylogenetic tree, with varying patterns of association.

We found little systematic evidence for non-additive contributions from raised IgE and non-allergic asthma to DA in allergic asthma, **Supp. Figure 5c** (Interactions).

Effects and phylogenetic context of four most common microbial families

The volcano plots in **Supp. Figure 6** expand on patterns of significant associations in **Supp. Figure 5c** and add the direction of association. *Streptococcaceae* taxa are almost universally overabundant in exposed participants, and definitely for all statistically significantly DA taxa, with increasing strength from asthma-only to IgE+ allergic to allergic asthma. Associations for DA *Lachnospiraceae* species are balanced between under- and overabundance for the asthma-only group, but universally overabundant in the allergic asthma group. Patterns of association are less clear for DA *Ruminococcoceae* and *Bacteroidaceae* taxa, partly due to the smaller number of DA taxa.

Supp. Figure 7 puts the taxa from the four most commonly differentially abundant families into the phylogenetic context of their respective families. 63 of 169 assessed *Streptococcaceae* taxa (37%) have statistically significant evidence for differential abundance, with associations concentrated across the largest sub-tree including the most closely related taxa. This is followed by *Ruminococcoceae*, where 17/110 (15%) have evidence for differential abundance, with the signal for the asthma-only and the IgE+ allergic group concentrated in different sub-trees. Both *Bacteroidaceae* and *Lachnospiraceae* taxa show lower level of enrichment with DA taxa of about 10% (16/165 and 40/404, respectively), with little evident phylogenetic grouping of the DA taxa.

Comments

In this Swedish twin study using shotgun sequencing on fecal samples, we found no evidence for differences in the overall gut microbial richness or composition between healthy controls and children diagnosed with allergic asthma, asthma only or IgE sensitization only. Feature-based analysis revealed a comparatively small number of taxa differentially abundant between healthy controls and exposed children, concentrated in microbial families *Streptococaceae*, *Lachnospiraceae*, *Ruminococaceae* and *Bacteroidaceae*. The strongest signal was observed for members of the family *Streptococaceae*, which showed the largest enrichment with differentially abundant species and consistent overabundance among exposed children. The joint effect of raised IgE and asthma on differential abundance in allergic asthma was almost exclusively additive, with no systematic evidence for synergistic or antagonistic effects.

Comparison with previous studies

In our study, gut microbial richness and diversity was similar between patients with allergic asthma or asthma only and healthy controls. This finding is similar to some studies [12, 35] but converse to others [36, 37]. We have summarized the bacterial lineages reported in previous studies and their correspondence with our ANSCOMB results in **Supp. Table 4**.

In a study examining gut microbiome and asthma endotypes, Zou et al (n=67) [2, 36], found no difference in alpha diversity between allergic and non-allergic asthmatic patients, however, they identified 28 species differing between the two groups, with a combination of *Ruminococcus sp*, *Brevundimonas sp* and *Clostridium disporicum* being associated with the asthma only endotypes [36]. Similarly Hsieh et al [35], found a lack of fecal microbiome richness and diversity between pediatric asthma and control participants (ages 9-17 years, n=80). Instead, children with asthma exhibited an altered host IgA response by gut bacteria compared with control participants [35]. This loss of IgA binding was prominently associated with members of genus *Blautia*, genus *Ruminococcus*, and family *Lachnospiraceae*. However, the authors did not distinguish between the different asthma subtypes or examine the role of IgE. In a study on murine models [38] and two reviews [2, 39] showed that allergic asthma, defined by the presence of both allergic sensitization and asthma, has more commonly been associated with a high relative abundance of the fungal taxa *Candida* and *Rhodotorula sp* during the first 6 months of life [38]. Fungi may be potential allergens and inducers of allergic inflammation, however, the bacterial taxa *Lachnospiraceae*, *Escherichia/Shigella*, *Veillonella* and *Faecalibacterium* have also been seen in a greater relative abundance in other studies on asthma and wheezing [2, 39], **Supp. Table 4**.

There are different potential mechanisms that can explain our findings. Allergic sensitization studies conducted in children < 6 months have shown more consistency in their microbial abundance and richness than studies conducted in older children [9, 12, 40]. The differences appear to be less apparent with increasing age [12], making it less likely for differences to be evident in older children when it stabilizes. This suggests the presence of critical period in early life during which gut colonization causes immune dysregulation and consequently susceptibility to disease [9, 41, 42].

Another hypothesis, is that fungal dysbiosis may play an important role in allergic disease [40]. Fungal species potentially experience an ecological advantage after antibiotic treatment in young children – antibiotics use in early childhood are a risk factor for asthma onset [40]. It is postulated that a deregulated interplay between gut bacteria and fungi may drive atopic disease [43]. Additionally, the metagenome of allergic diseases may have a higher pro-inflammatory potential in children with early life dysbiosis, and a decreased biosynthesis of anti-inflammatory short chain fatty acids [44]. We did not test for this in our study. We also observed considerable variation in microbial composition due to differences between twin pairs. Co-twins, like other siblings, generally have more similar gut microbiomes to each other compared to unrelated individuals [45].

Strengths and Limitations

This cohort study has several strengths including the use of high quality questionnaire data and a validated outcome. Shotgun sequencing enables a hypothesis-free approach that helps to identify the complete taxonomical and functional profile of an organism. These can be determined from very low volumes of the sample. Further, this is the first twin study on the gut microbiome using shotgun metagenomics with an allergic asthma outcome, and thus is an important contribution to the existing literature. Studies that do not adjust for differences in genetic or environmental drivers of microbial diversity that are covered by the twin status are open to significant familial and/or environmental confounding. Further we were able to replicate some findings observed in previous studies on asthma, **Supp. Table 4**.

Important limitations include the cross-sectional design that only allowed a snapshot of factors across the different phenotypes. Further, while shotgun sequencing improves taxonomic inference compared to amplicon results, inference is still limited by our knowledge about taxonomy. Another possible limitation is the lack of medication information, although most children with asthma typically use asthma controllers on a regular basis. Additionally, cross-species misclassification remains a challenge. We also did not investigate the role of either archaeal, fungal or viral microbial diversity.

In this adolescent twin study investigating the association between the gut microbiome and allergic asthma, there was overall little or no difference in species richness or composition between children with allergic asthma and healthy controls. We found n=201 taxa that were statistically significantly differentially abundant between the healthy control group and at least one of the three exposure levels, with almost exclusively additive effects. Many differences in microbial composition between children could be attributed to differences between twin pairs. The strongest signal showing differentially abundant microbial families associated with allergic asthma were the members of the family *Streptococcaceae* and *Lachnospiraceae*.

Ethics Statement

All data was pseudonymised prior to analysis. Study participants were not involved in the planning or writing of this research project. Ethical approval was obtained for this project from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority with diary number 2012/250-32.

Consent

The authors assert that all the procedures contributing to this work comply with the ethical standards of the relevant National and institutional committees on human experimentation and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2008. Informed consent for the study was obtained from all the participants and their parents.

Data availability statement

Due to ethical and data integrity concerns, individual-level data cannot be made openly available. Further information about the data and conditions for access are available at the Swedish Twin Registry, Department of Medical Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden.

Conflict of Interest

The Center for Translational Microbiome Research, Department of Microbiology, Tumor and Cell Biology, Karolinska Institutet, is part funded by Ferring Pharmaceuticals. The other authors report no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary Figures

Supp. Figure 1: Data flow chart

Supp. Figure 2: Number of reads per sample, by exposure group.

Supp. Figure 3: Microbial abundance of families across exposure groups

Supp. Figure 4: Alpha-diversity by exposure level for the Shannon- and Simpson index

Supp. Figure 5: Differentially abundant taxa across exposure groups

Supp. Figure 6: Volcano plots for the four most common microbial families

Supp. Figure 7: Annotated phylogenetic trees for the four most common microbial families

Supplementary Tables

Supp. Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study cohort

Supp. Table 2: PERMANOVA summary tables for comparing beta-diversity across exposure levels, including the R^2 values for the individual parameters.

Supp. Table 3: ANCOMBC results for all OTUs, including taxonomic classifications, effect sizes and p-values for each exposure group, provided as separate spreadsheet file with one sheet per exposure group

Supp. Table 4: overview of bacterial lineages associated with asthma in previous studies and comparison with our ANCOMBS results

Supp. Figure 1: Data flow chart for the STOPPA twin cohort displaying number of children with microbiome samples (N=355) and quality-filtering due to failed assays; low sequencing depth; low abundance or prevalence. Data set A describes the quality-filtered raw data (N=339); data set B the rarefied data for diversity analysis (N=339) and data set C the feature-based analysis (N=317).

Supp. Figure 2: Number of reads per sample, by exposure group. Distribution of number of reads per sample, both for the full cohort (n =339) and separately by exposure group; numbers are shown on log10-scale.

Supp. Figure 3: Microbial abundance of families across exposure groups. For the full cohort (n =339) and separately by exposure group, including missing exposure status, as percentages of total reads in each group (Data set A in Supp. Figure 1). The 11 most common families are shown in order of abundance, with all other families collapsed as *Other*.

Supp. Figure 4: Alpha diversity measures by clinical phenotype. Shannon and Simpson alpha diversity was calculated across exposure groups, excluding missing values ($n = 317$). Unadjusted values are as estimated, adjusted values are adjusted via a linear mixed model including a fixed effect for sequencing run and a per-twin pair random intercept. P-values are for a joint null hypothesis for no mean difference between exposure groups (unadjusted: Wald test for a simple linear regression model with robust standard errors adjusted for between-twin correlation, adjusted: sequential F-test for the mixed model, with Satterthwaite degrees of freedom).

Supp. Figure 5: Differentially abundant taxa across exposure groups (n=201). The results of the feature-based analysis are derived from data set C (Figure 1). **A:** Venn diagram showing the overlap of differentially abundant taxa across exposure groups. **B:** Distribution of microbial families among differentially abundant taxa across exposure groups, showing the proportion of taxa per family for each exposure level. **C:** Phylogenetic tree for differentially abundant taxa. The outer annotation ring codes for the microbial families; the innermost ring (in red) indicates a statistically significant association (at false discovery rate \leq 1%) for the three exposure groups asthma-only, allergy-only (IgE+), and allergic asthma. The intermediate ring (in blue) indicates a statistically significant (at FDR \leq 1%) non-additive joint effect of IgE+ and allergy in the allergic asthma group.

Supp. Figure 6: Volcano plots for the four most common microbial families among differentially abundant taxa as per Supp. Figure 5b. Each panel plots statistical significance (as $-\log_{10}$ of FDR) against the \log_2 of the fold change relative to the healthy controls. The plots show all analyzed taxa for each family, indicating statistical significance at the 1% FDR level by shape and transparency: non-statistically significant taxa are shown as transparent, with darker regions indicating over-plotting, showing the overall the distribution of taxa in the plot.

Streptococcaceae (63/169)

Lachnospiraceae (40/404)

Ruminococcaceae (17/110)

Bacteroidaceae (16/165)

FDR \leq 0.01

Yes
No

Supp. Figure 7: Annotated phylogenetic trees for the four most common microbial families among differentially abundant taxa. For each family shown in Figure 4, we show the phylogenetic tree containing all family members that were included in the ANCOMBC analysis (i.e. not filtered out as part of the ANCOMBC preprocessing step). The annotation ring indicates a false discovery rate above or below 1% for the three exposure groups asthma-only, allergy-only (IgE+) and allergic asthma. The numbers in the subtitles correspond to the number of taxa found to be differentially abundant for at least one exposure vs. the number of taxa in the family included in the analysis.

Supp. Table 1: Baseline Characteristics for the 317 twins. There are 129 pairs of twins (258 children).

	Total Population	Neither: IgE<0.35 and no asthma	Asthma only	IgE ≥ 0.35 only	Asthma and IgE ≥ 0.35
Characteristics					
Number (%)	317 (100)	165 (52.0)	18 (5.7)	91 (28.7)	43 (13.6)
Age in years, Mean (SD)	12.0 (1.5)	12.5 (1.4)	12.0 (1.8)	12.3 (1.4)	12.6 (1.5)
Sex					
<i>Male</i>	177 (55.8)	80 (48.5)	6 (33.3)	63 (69.2)	28 (65.1)
Full Twin pairs					
<i>Yes</i>	258 (81)	136 (82.4)	17 (94.4)	74 (81.3)	31 (72.1)
<i>No*</i>	59 (19)	29 (17.6)	1 (5.6)	17 (18.7)	12 (27.9)
Zygoty					
<i>Monozygous</i>	173 (54.6)	89 (53.4)	10 (55.6)	49 (53.8)	25 (58.1)
<i>Dizygous</i>	144 (45.4)	76 (46.1)	8 (44.4)	42 (46.2)	18 (41.9)
Birthweight					
<i>Weight (mean, (SD))</i>	2613.5 (568.7)	2605.6 (578.4)	2503.5 (426.0)	2640.2 (552.3)	2639.9 (636.9)
Intrauterine tobacco exposure					
<i>No</i>	251 (79.2)	126 (76.4)	17 (94.4)	69 (75.8)	39 (90.8)
<i>Yes</i>	26 (8.2)	14 (8.5)	1 (5.6)	9 (9.8)	2 (4.6)
<i>Missing</i>	40 (12.6)	25 (15.1)	0 (0.0)	13 (14.4)	2 (4.6)
Mode of delivery					
<i>Vaginal Delivery</i>	168 (53.0)	88 (53.3)	10 (55.6)	41 (47.2)	27 (62.8)
<i>Cesarean Section</i>	130 (41.0)	65 (39.4)	8 (44.4)	43 (45.1)	16 (37.2)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (6.0)	12 (7.3)	0 (0.0)	7 (7.7)	0 (0.0)

Supp. Table 2: PERMANOVA results for differences in beta-diversity between exposure groups. Contributions of different variables to explaining differences in species diversity between samples: R^2 = proportion of variance explained, p-value = permutation p-value for the hypothesis of no explanation (B=1000 permutations), df = degrees of freedom. Residual refers to the unexplained (“error”) variance in beta diversity after accounting for the contribution of all other variables. We show results for three difference beta diversity measures: Unifrac (phylogenetically aware, differences in absence/presence), weighted Unifrac (phylogenetically aware, differences in abundance), Bray-Curtis (differences in absence/presence, does not include phylogenetic information).

Model	Variable	df	Unifrac		Weighted Unifrac		Bray-Curtis	
			R^2	p-value	R^2	p-value	R^2	p-value
Unadjusted	Exposure	3	0.01	0.30	0.01	0.41	0.01	0.14
	Residual	313	0.99		0.99		0.99	
Adjusted	Sequencing run	7	0.033	0.001	0.018	0.238	0.025	0.001
	Sampling site	4	0.016	0.001	0.018	0.020	0.014	0.001
	Twin pair	183	0.657	0.001	0.692	0.001	0.708	0.001
	Exposure	3	0.007	0.741	0.005	0.672	0.008	0.040
	Residual	119	0.288		0.266		0.246	

df: degrees of freedom

Supp. Table 3: separate spreadsheet listing the results for the ANCOMBC DA-analysis for all n=1,969 species remaining after prevalence filtering (**data set (C)**, Supp. **Figure 1**), for all three exposure groups, each in a separate sheet. See file *Supptab3_ANCOMBC_taxLists.xlsx*, available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7998496>

Supp. Table 4. Bacterial lineages associated with asthma in previous studies, in comparison with results from our ANSCOMB analysis

Study	Ref.	Exposure age	Result reported in the literature				Results in our ANSCOMB analysis				Medication	
			Outcome age	Population size	Phenotype	Differentially abundant	Taxonomy	Asthma only	IgE+	Allergic asthma		Total present
Hsieh et al (2021)	35	9 to 17 years	9 to 17 years	40 asthma, 40 healthy	Asthma, IgA response	<i>Blautia</i>	genus	5	2	0	28	inconsistent use of medication
						<i>Ruminococcus</i>	genus	4	10	2	54	
						<i>Lachnospiraceae</i>	family	46	25	32	404	
Zou et al (2021)	36	18 to 50 years	cross-sectional study	47 asthma, 20 healthy	Asthma only	<i>Ruminococcus sp</i>	species	0	0	0	5	new patients, treatment naive
						<i>Brevundimonas sp</i>	species	0	0	0	1	
						<i>Clostridium disporicum</i>	species	0	0	0	1	
Fujimura et al (2014)	38	murine models	cross-sectional study	/	Asthma, allergic sensitization	<i>Candida</i>	genus	0	0	0	0	n/a
						<i>Rhodotorula sp</i>	species	0	0	0	0	
Fujimura et al (2015)	2, 39	Review	Review	/	Asthma, wheezing	<i>Lachnospiraceae</i>	family	46	25	32	404	
Zimmermann et al (2019)		Review				<i>Escherichia</i>	genus	0	0	0	11	
						<i>Shigella</i>	genus	0	0	0	0	
						<i>Veillonella</i>	genus	2	1	0	14	
						<i>Faecalibacterium</i>	genus	6	0	3	13	
Arrieta et al (2018)	12	5 years	case-control	27 asthma, 90 healthy	Atopic wheeze (surrogate for asthma risk)	<i>Veillonella</i>	genus	2	1	0	14	not mentioned
						<i>Ruminococcus</i>	genus	4	10	2	54	

Legend
Study, Ref.: the study as referenced in the Discussion (note that 2 and 40 are discussed jointly)
Exposure age: when exposure (microbiome) was measured
Outcome age: when outcome (phenotype) was measured
Phenotype: outcomes as described in the Discussion
Differentially abundant: the taxonomic taxa overabundant in the subjects having the outcome phenotype
Taxonomy: the level of taxonomy at which the outcome was reported
Asthma only: the number of species with a matching taxonomic level statistically significant at $FDR \leq 5\%$ for children with asthma only (more relaxed for a replication effort)
IgE+: same, but significant at $FDR \leq 5\%$ in children with IgE+ only
Allergic asthma: same but for allergic asthma
Total present: total number of species with the corresponding annotation in data used for ANCOMBC (out of n=1,969 total)
Medication: if study reports any medication.